

Application of Cognitive Intelligence in Mphasis using Cognitive Guru

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ABSTRACT

Over the years machines have been helping us to easily solve problems. These machines have algorithms and greater computing power by using technologies. The most popular technologies used nowadays are Machine Learning, Cognitive Intelligence, and Artificial Intelligence which may change the way businesses operate and how they make decisions. Most intelligence machines can reason and process natural language on statistical, logical, and operational methods. By offering better and efficient solutions to several business tasks, these intelligent machines allow businesses to boost productivity and offer a better experience to customers. Mphasis provides information technology services and integrated solutions. It includes infrastructure technology, application services, and business process outsourcing.

Keywords: Mphasis, Cognitive intelligence, chatbot, Artificial Intelligence

COGNITIVE INTELLIGENCE

Cognitive intelligence is one's ability to learn, solve problems, and make sound judgments, particularly as contrasted with emotional intelligence. It is important in analysing Financial, Marketing, Government and Healthcare Data. AI is important in service-oriented industries such as Healthcare, Manufacturing and Customer Service. The human brain can digest information and form intelligence and meaning. Cognitive intelligence uses existing knowledge that grows with practice and different experiences.^[1] Cognitive Intelligence covers the technological areas and tools allowing the applications, websites, bots to see, hear, speak and understand the needs of the user through natural language, thereby making the machines to learn their users' language.

Chatbot is an automated program taking voice commands or text chats or both to initiate the human conversation, their interaction with customers being like a human and cost little to nothing to engage with. The chatbots are used in a various sections- the retail bots designed to pick and order groceries, weather bots for weather forecasts of the day or week, and simply friendly bots that talk to people in need of a friend.^[2] Their use in business is increased as to automate customer service through messaging apps and phone calls. Organizations get clear return on investment using the Chabots. They also help in online access of Website popups and virtual assistants.

Classification of the chatbots are done on the basis of their usage in commercial, educational, entertainment, financial, health, news, and production areas.^[3]

Limitations of Chatbots^[3]

- Chatbots cannot deal unsaved query as the database used for output generation is fixed and limited.
- Efficiency depends on language processing and can fail because of the irregularities like accents and mistakes in language.
- Are unable to deal with multiple questions at the same time hence conversational opportunities are limited.
- Training requires large amount of conversational data.
- Cannot manage non-linear conversations with a user.

Mphasis

In India, there have been organizations with key establishments in the AI space. IISc has organizations with driving organizations like Robert Bosch, Faurecia; IIT Bangalore is in association with Mphasis to set up the focus of Cognitive Computing; IIT Kharagpur has set up AI inquire about focus with Capillary Technologies.^[4]

Mphasis applies next-generation technology to help enterprises transform businesses globally. Customer centricity is foundational to Mphasis and is reflected in the Mphasis' Front2Back™ Transformation approach. Front2Back™ uses the exponential power of cloud and cognitive to provide a hyper-personalized (C=X2C2TM=1) digital experience to clients and their end customers.^[5]

COGNITIVE SOLUTIONS

Big data management and advanced analytics are now central to business competitiveness. Mphasis is enabling enterprises to harness the power of data using the accelerators and products by NEXTLabs and NextAngles, and Mphasis Digital solutions.

Enterprises are increasingly looking for a bot platform as it enables them to create intelligent, conversational bots in a simple manner. These platforms simplify development, enable standardization, drive usability, improve time-to-market and optimize costs.

CognitiveGuru (CG) is an AI-based chatbot development platform, built using Microsoft AI and popular open-source technologies to enable enterprises to design, build, establish and deploy chatbots in an easy manner. Incubating the workforce of the future, CG is an intuitive virtual assistant platform, powered by cognitive 'Talents'. These Talents, written using NodeJS, perform specific tasks such as resetting a password, or fetching specific information and are categorized based on domain – banking, airlines, healthcare, insurance, government and society, and function – sales & marketing, service desk, human resources, and products.^[6]

Mphasis CG provides:

- Enriched intent and entity identification in utterances through NLP and NLU technologies

- Secured integration with any system within the enterprise through REST or SOAP APIs exposed by the existing systems
- Real-time analytics on the usage of Talents by authorized users

Cognitive Guru in various functions^[6]

Service Desk

Service desk operation adopted chatbots at an early stage to reduce the resolution time of high-priority issues. CG as an interface establishes the possibility of end-to-end or zero-touch automation from request to fulfillment, through features such as seamless integration with core systems on a secured architecture. In addition to the end-users, CG bots benefit service desk leaders, service desk operations managers, service desk support managers, and service desk support analysts. It currently handles more than 50+ service desk use cases, catering to 28,000+ employees, and thus helps in dropping the call wait time by 50%, lowering the cost by 30%, increasing the productivity by 30%, reducing the call volume by 40%.

Human Resource

A virtual assistant is undoubtedly the best channel for HRs to providing real-time and accurate responses to employees' queries. CG bots streamline and personalize the experience across different workforce categories, within an enterprise. It is a virtual guide for employees that sails through information residing in multiple systems. In addition to the workforce, CG benefits HR leaders, HR business partners, and functions including employee engagement, compensation & benefits, and learning & development. It is widely used for recruitment, employee onboarding, policy queries, leave management, employee appreciation, among others, and helps in improving SLA(Service Level Administration) by 50%, and turnaround time by 40%, increasing customer satisfaction score by 60%, reducing the call/ticket volume by 50%.

Sales and Marketing

Bots have immense potential to boost user engagement, consequently leading to more conversion and sales. CG bots hyper-personalize the conversational experience for the end-user, elevating the connection between the services/products and users to the next level. While the businesses stand to benefit at large, CG benefits lead management, promotional campaign, customer engagement, target marketing, and customer support teams in driving revenue and growth. It helps in improving the request closures by 50%, increasing the targeted promotions by 30%, enhancing customer engagement by 50%, ensuring the assistance available 24 X 7.

Product Engineering

CG bots bring in the conversational experience augmented with cognitive insights which allow product managers to provide hyper-personalized self-services at ease. The bots entitle the product managers to integrate with enterprise product recommendation engines to extend hyper-personalized service based on customer profiles. It benefits product administrators, product analysts, product support engineers, and product managers -reducing the number of

clicks required to do things by 70%, training efforts by 50%, lowering the support desk call volume by 30%, improving customer satisfaction score by 50%.

Mphasis SWOT analysis

The SWOT analysis of Mphasis has helped to benchmark its business & performance.

Strengths^[7]

- Rising Net Cash Flow and Cash from Operating activity
- Growth in Net Profit with increasing Profit Margin (QoQ)
- Employment strength of 38000 with presence in 14 countries

Weaknesses^[8]

- Companies with growing costs YoY for long term projects
- Shareholding decreased by the promoter
- increase in direct sales has to lead to margin pressure increase

Opportunities^[9]

- Brokers upgraded recommendation or target price in the past three months
- Positive Breakout First Resistance (LTP > R1)
- Highest Recovery from 52 Week Low

Threats^[10]

- Increasing Trend in Non-Core Income
- A slowdown in US economy as major client base is from US^[11]
- Attrition and Employee loyalty^[11]

Conclusion

Chatbots have achieved its mainstream adoption in every sector. It has brought drastic changes in human-computer interactions and customer service in India. Along with making execution of a task easier, it has also brought convenience in the way queries are solved.

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